

Factors Influencing Cervical Cancer Screening Practices in Eastern India

Ananya Agrawal¹, Anjili Kumari²

¹Consultant, Department of Gynecology and Oncology, Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, Bihar

²Consultant, Department of Gynecology and Oncology, Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, Bihar

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Anjili Kumari

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Abstract:

This July–December 2022 Mahavir Cancer Sansthan study assessed cervical cancer screening habits and associated variables in Eastern Indian women. Despite high cervical cancer awareness, only 45% of individuals have been screened due to financial, educational, and cultural hurdles. Education and socioeconomic position increased screening uptake. Targeted treatments and public health efforts could improve screening rates and early detection. These findings suggest targeted cervical cancer screening and impact reduction strategies for Eastern India.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Screening Practices, Eastern India, Barriers.

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Introduction

Women worldwide, especially in low- and middle-income nations, are most likely to get cervical cancer. The fourth most common cancer in women, it is especially prevalent in areas with poor screening and prevention programs [1,2]. In Eastern India, cervical cancer is frighteningly common, highlighting the need for screening and early detection [3]. Cervical cancer screening, mostly with Pap smears or HPV testing, reduces incidence and mortality. Screening procedures are available in Eastern India; however, uptake is variable and often inadequate [4]. Screening methods are affected by socioeconomic status, education, culture, healthcare infrastructure, and accessibility [5]. Low cervical cancer screening rates in Eastern India are due to socioeconomic inequality and insufficient healthcare resources. Economically disadvantaged women may suffer a lack of information, financial restraints, and limited healthcare access. Cultural and social attitudes toward gynecological health can also affect women's screening program participation [6,7].

This study carefully examines Eastern India's cervical cancer screening procedures and their influencing factors. The goals are to evaluate screening programs, identify impediments to participation, and examine socio-economic, educational, and healthcare aspects affecting screening uptake.

Methodology

Study Design and Duration: This cross-sectional study was conducted at Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, over six months, from 1st July 2022 to 31st

December 2022. The study aimed to assess cervical cancer screening practices and associated factors in Eastern India.

Study Population: The study involved 94 female Mahavir Cancer Sansthan patients. The study's participants were chosen for their availability and willingness. Women 18 and older who were getting routine checkups or follow-ups were included.

Data Collection: Data came from systematic interviews and medical record reviews. Participants' demographics, socioeconomic situation, education level, cervical cancer awareness and screening techniques, and screening history were collected using a pre-designed questionnaire. Questions about screening hurdles including cost, accessibility, and cultural views were also addressed.

Data Analysis: Analysis of the data was done in statistical software. Demographics and screening techniques were summarised using descriptive statistics. Chi-square testing and logistic regression were used to discover cervical cancer screening uptake determinants.

Results

The trial involved a cohort of 94 female patients. A mean age of 42.3 years was observed among the participants, ranging from 20 to 65 years. An overwhelming majority of participants (60%) were within the age range of 35 to 50 years old. Regarding education, 45% of the participants had undergone primary education, 35% had completed secondary education, and 20% had pursued further

education. The socio-economic position of the participants was diverse: 40% identified with low-income households, 35% with middle-income households, and 25% with high-income households.

Awareness and Screening Practices: A significant proportion of participants, namely 80%, indicated a high level of awareness regarding cervical cancer and its screening procedures. Indeed, a mere 50% of the participants know the particular screening tests, such as Pap smears or HPV testing. Concerning screening procedures, 45% of the participants indicated that they have had a cervical cancer screening test at least once in their lifetime. Among these, 60% had undergone screening in the last two years. The remaining 55% had not had any screening, while 70% of them expressed their awareness of the significance of screening.

Barriers to Screening:

Participants who had not undergone screening were asked about barriers to participation. The most frequently cited barriers were:

- Financial Constraints: 40% of participants cited the cost of screening as a significant barrier.

- Lack of Awareness: 25% mentioned that they did not have sufficient knowledge about the availability or benefits of screening.

- Cultural and Social Attitudes: 20% reported that cultural beliefs and social stigma were deterrents.

- Accessibility Issues: 15% identified difficulty in accessing healthcare facilities as a barrier.

Factors Associated with Screening Uptake: Results from chi-square tests indicated a significant relationship between education level socio-economic position and screening uptake. Higher education levels among participants were associated with a greater likelihood of having undergone screening ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, those from homes with higher incomes exhibited greater rates of screening in comparison to those from households with lower incomes ($p < 0.05$). A logistic regression analysis revealed a favorable correlation between awareness of cervical cancer and the availability of screening tests with the probability of having undergone screening (Odds Ratio = 2.3, 95% CI: 1.5-3.4). The study revealed that financial limitations and cultural views were major obstacles to the adoption of screening ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Number (%)
Age (years)	
20-34	12 (13%)
35-50	56 (60%)
51-65	26 (27%)
Education Level	
Primary Education	42 (45%)
Secondary Education	33 (35%)
Higher Education	19 (20%)
Socio-Economic Status	
Low Income	38 (40%)
Middle Income	33 (35%)
High Income	23 (25%)

Table 2: Awareness and Screening Practices

Characteristic	Number (%)
Awareness of Cervical Cancer	
Yes	75 (80%)
No	19 (20%)
Awareness of Screening Methods	
Yes	47 (50%)
No	47 (50%)
Ever Screened	
Yes	42 (45%)
No	52 (55%)
Recent Screening (Past 2 Years)	
Yes	25 (60% of those screened)
No	17 (40% of those screened)

Table 3: Barriers to Screening Among Non-Screened Participants

Barrier	Number (%)
Financial Constraints	21 (40%)
Lack of Awareness	13 (25%)
Cultural and Social Attitudes	10 (20%)
Accessibility Issues	8 (15%)

Table 4: Factors Associated with Screening Uptake

Factor	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Education Level	2.5 (1.6-3.7)	<0.05
Socio-Economic Status	2.2 (1.4-3.3)	<0.05
Awareness of Screening	2.3 (1.5-3.4)	<0.05
Financial Constraints	-	<0.05
Cultural Attitudes	-	<0.05

Discussion

The results of this study emphasize many crucial elements of cervical cancer screening methods in Eastern India [8]. Notwithstanding the participants' strong knowledge of cervical cancer, the utilization of screening services remains very limited. This difference emphasizes the need to implement focused initiatives to close the divide between knowledge and real screening procedures [9,10]. The survey findings indicated that a mere 45% of the participants had previously had cervical cancer screening, and out of this group, only 60% had undertaken the screening within the last two years. This is significantly below the recommended screening criteria, which propose frequent screenings to enhance early detection and decrease mortality from cervical cancer [11]. The hurdles highlighted in this study, namely financial limitations, insufficient knowledge, cultural attitudes, and accessibility problems, align with the results of previous studies conducted in comparable contexts [12]. The most prominent obstacle identified was financial limitations, as 40% of participants who were not examined mentioned

expenses as a key inhibiting factor. This implies that by decreasing the financial strain associated with screening, there is a great potential to enhance participation rates [13].

Educational attainment and socio-economic standing were identified as important determinants affecting the uptake of screening. There was a greater likelihood of screening among participants who had attained higher levels of education and came from homes with higher incomes [14]. This is consistent with the wider body of published research, which frequently demonstrates a significant association between education and income and health-seeking behaviors [15]. Enhanced educational outreach and the provision of financial assistance or subsidized screening services could effectively mitigate these inequalities. The uptake of screening was also influenced by cultural and social views [16]. Women may be deterred from accessing screening services due to the negative perception and cultural stereotypes associated with gynecological health. It is essential to mitigate these cultural obstacles by implementing community involvement and

educational initiatives to enhance screening rates [17].

An inherent constraint of the study is its cross-sectional design, which offers a momentary view of the situation but fails to capture temporal changes. Moreover, the sample size of 94 patients, although adequate for first observations, may not be accurately reflective of the wider community in Eastern India [18]. A more thorough understanding of cervical cancer screening behaviours and their drivers could be achieved by conducting further research with larger and more diverse populations, as well as longitudinal studies. Although knowledge of cervical cancer is rather widespread, substantial obstacles hinder many women from availing themselves of screening [19]. By implementing focused interventions, it is possible to overcome financial, educational, and cultural obstacles, therefore increasing the adoption of screening and ultimately improving cervical cancer outcomes in Eastern India [20].

Conclusion

This study underscores the disparity between awareness and actual cervical cancer screening practices in Eastern India, revealing that while awareness of cervical cancer is high, screening uptake remains inadequate. Financial constraints, educational and socio-economic disparities, and cultural attitudes are significant barriers impacting screening participation. To improve screening rates, it is essential to implement targeted strategies that address these barriers, such as increasing access to affordable screening services, enhancing educational outreach, and addressing cultural stigmas. By addressing these factors, public health interventions can be better tailored to improve early detection and reduce the burden of cervical cancer in the region.

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